

Beckmann Rearrangement of the Oximes of 3-Aryl-4-Aroyl Butyric Acids and Synthesis of 3-(2'-Methoxy-5'-Methylphenyl)-4-Aminobutyric Acid

D. N. CHATURVEDI and R. A. KULKARNI*

Chemistry Research Lab., Ramnarain Ruia College, Matunga, Bombay-400019.

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A series of oximes of 3-aryl-4-aroyl butyric acids were synthesised which on Beckmann rearrangement gave corresponding N-aryl-4-(2'-methoxy-5'-methylphenyl)-2-pyrrolidones. These pyrrolidones were then converted into 3-(2'-methoxy-5'-methylphenyl)-4-arylamido butyric acids. Drastic hydrolysis of these amido acids yielded 3-(2'-methoxy-5'-methylphenyl)-4-amino butyric acid.

In view of the anti-inflammatory¹, herbicidal², anti-spasmodic³ and analeptic⁴ activities of N-aryl-2-pyrrolidones a series of N-aryl-2-pyrrolidones (VI) were prepared. Identification of GABA as an important brain constituent⁵ which act as an inhibitory neurotransmitter⁶ to regulate CNS excitation⁷ and its anticonvulsive activities⁸ stimulated our additional interest to the hydrolytic transformation of these pyrrolidones to substituted GABA, 3-(2'-methoxy-5'-methylphenyl)-4-aminobutyric acid (VIII).

3-(2'-methoxy-5'-methylphenyl)-4-aroyl butyric acids⁹ (Table 1)† on reaction with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in alkaline medium afforded the corresponding oximes (Table 2)††. The oximes (II) were characterised by elemental analysis and I.R. spectrum. 'syn-aryl' configuration was assigned to these oximes on the basis of the product obtained after Beckmann rearrangement.

Beckmann rearrangement of the oximes using conc.

TABLE 1—M. P.S AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF 3-(2'-METHOXY-5'-METHYLPHENYL)-4-AROYL BUTYRIC ACIDS (I)

No	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	R ₆	m.p.* °C	Yield** %	Molecular formula	C%		H%	
									Found	Required	Found	Req.
a	H	H	OAc	H	H	84-5	52	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₅	70.8	70.7	6.7	6.7
b	OMe	H	Me	H	OMe	92-3	57	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ O ₅	68.2	68.3	6.8	6.7
c	Me	H	OAc	Prop	H	115-6	61	C ₂₅ H ₃₂ O ₅	73.0	72.8	7.8	7.7

* All compounds were recrystallised from dilute acetic acid.

** Yields obtained by using Nitrobenzene as a solvent in Friedel-Crafts reactions.

TABLE 2—M.P.S AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF OXIMES OF 3-(2'-METHOXY-5'-METHYLPHENYL)-4-AROYLBUTYRIC ACIDS (II)

No	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	R ₆	m.p.* °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	N%	
									Found	Required
a	H	H	OAc	H	H	162-3	79	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ NO ₅	3.6	3.7
b	Me	H	OMe	H	H	150-1	76	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ NO ₅	3.8	3.7
c	OMe	H	H	Me	H	190-1	84	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ NO ₅	3.6	3.7
d	OMe	H	Me	H	OMe	182-3	75	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ NO ₅	3.4	3.4
e	Me	H	OMe	Prop	H	155-6	83	C ₂₄ H ₃₁ NO ₅	3.1	3.3
f	Me	H	OAc	Prop	H	177-8	85	C ₂₆ H ₃₃ NO ₅	3.2	3.2
g	H	H	OPh	H	H	179-80	78	C ₂₆ H ₃₃ NO ₅	3.3	3.3

* All compounds were recrystallised from dilute ethanol.

† Other aroyl butyric acids are reported in literature (ref. 9).

†† Remaining 4 corresponding oximes are cited in literature (ref. 9).

H₂SO₄ gave dark resinous material while tosyl chloride gave back the unchanged oximes even under variety of conditions. Other acidic reagents such as phosphorus pentachloride and thionyl chloride were, therefore, employed but the highest yield was obtained using polyphosphoric acid. Migration of the 3-aryl butyric acid group to the nitrogen atom (*anti*-rearrangement) would result in the formation of III. This would eliminate a molecule of water, either directly to yield a azalactone (IV) or undergo a prototropic shift to V and then suffer a water loss to form the butyrolactam (VI) (Table 3). The butyrolactam structure was confirmed through its elemental analysis, I.R., N.M.R. and Mass spectra.

Mild hydrolysis of VI with ethanolic alkali yielded the amido acids (VII) (Table 4) which on drastic hydrolysis gave two fragments, identified as 3-aryl-4-aminobutyric acid (VIII) and anisic acid (IX). The hydrolysis of VII was not affected even with conc. HCl or H₂SO₄.

The various substituents -OCH₃,¹-OC₂H₅, etc., on the aryl nucleus had no effect on the course of the Beckmann rearrangement as the nature of the products of the *anti*-rearrangement and products of hydrolysis was the same in all cases.

Pyrrolidones(VI) have shown promising *anti*-inflammatory activity while the pharmacological evaluation of GABA (VIII) is in progress.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded on a Gallen-Kamp melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. I.R. spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer infrachord or Beckmann I.R. spectro photometer. N.M.R. spectra were recorded on a Varian A-60 spectrometer with tetramethyl silane (TMS) as an internal standard. Mass spectra were recorded with a CH-7 Varian Mass spectrometer. The ionizing voltage was 70 e.v. and the ion source temperature 150°.

Oxime (IIa) of 3-(2'-methoxy-5'-methylphenyl)-4-(4'-methoxybenzoyl) butyric acid (Ia) :

3.39 g (0.01 m) of keto acid (Ia) was dissolved in 1N NaOH solution (20 ml). This was heated on a water bath with 0.735 g (0.01057 m) of hydroxylamine hydrochloride for about 30 min. Reaction mixture on cooling was acidified with dilute acidic acid to separate solid mass which was washed with water and crystallised from dil. ethanol in greenish needles (3.03 g), m.p. 172°, tlc 3 : 2 chloroform-ethylacetate. ir (KBr) : ν_{\max} . 3150-2850 (-OH), 1700 (C=O of carboxylic group), 1640 (C=N) and 945 (N-O) cm⁻¹.

Similar procedure has been adopted for the other oximes listed in Table 2.

N-(4'-methoxybenzoyl)-4-(2'-methoxy-5'-methylphenyl)-2-pyrrolidone (VIa) :

TABLE 3—M.P.S AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF N-ARYL-4-(2'-METHOXY-5'-METHYLPHENYL)-2-PYRROLIDONES (VI)

No	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	m.p.* °C	Yield** %	Molecular formula	N% Found	Required
a	H	H	OMe	H	H	165-6	70	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ NO ₄	4.1	4.1
b	H	H	OAc	H	H	120-1	62	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ NO ₄	3.8	3.9
c	H	Me	OMe	H	H	158-9	55	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ NO ₄	4.0	3.9
d	Me	H	OMe	H	H	129-30	65	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ NO ₄	3.8	3.9
e	OMe	H	H	Me	H	120-1	58	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ NO ₅	4.0	3.9
f	OMe	H	OMe	H	H	148-9	66	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ NO ₅	3.6	3.7
g	OMe	H	H	OMe	H	161-2	69	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ NO ₅	3.6	3.7
h	OMe	H	Me	H	OMe	158-9	60	C ₂₂ H ₂₇ NO ₅	3.7	3.6
i	Me	H	OMe	Prop	H	138-9	54	C ₂₄ H ₂₉ NO ₄	3.4	3.5
j	Me	H	OAc	Prop	H	166-7	59	C ₂₅ H ₃₁ NO ₄	3.5	3.4
k	H	H	OPh	H	H	169-70	68	C ₂₅ H ₂₉ NO ₄	3.5	3.4

* All compounds were recrystallised from ethanol.

** The yields obtained using PPA.

TABLE 4—M.P.S AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF 3-(2' METHOXY-5'-METHYLPHENYL)-4-ARYLAMIDOBUTYRIC ACIDS (VIII)

No	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	m.p.* °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	N% Found	Required
a	H	H	OMe	H	H	162-3	65	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ NO ₅	3.9	3.9
b	H	H	OAc	H	H	171-3	62	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ NO ₅	3.7	3.8
c	H	Me	OMe	H	H	191-2	49	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ NO ₅	3.7	3.7
d	Me	H	OMe	H	H	194-5	52	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ NO ₅	3.7	3.8
e	OMe	H	H	Me	H	162-3	48	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ NO ₅	3.7	3.8
f	OMe	H	OMe	H	H	182-3	55	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ NO ₅	3.7	3.6
g	OMe	H	H	OMe	H	201-2	61	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ NO ₆	3.6	3.6
h	OMe	H	Me	H	OMe	210-2	42	C ₂₂ H ₂₉ NO ₆	3.4	3.3
i	Me	H	OMe	n-Prop	H	186-7	49	C ₂₄ H ₃₁ NO ₅	3.4	3.3
j	Me	H	OAc	n-Prop	H	198-9	51	C ₂₅ H ₃₃ NO ₅	3.2	3.2
k	H	H	OPh	H	H	172-3	62	C ₂₅ H ₃₁ NO ₅	3.3	3.2

* All compounds were recrystallised from dilute ethanol. Satisfactory C,H analysis have been obtained for all the compounds.

(i) Using Phosphorus pentachloride—

1.8 g of phosphorus pentachloride (0.0086 m) was added in small portions to the well stirred solution of 3.57 g (0.01 m) of oxime (II) dissolved in dry tetrahydrofuran (50 ml) at ice-cooled and moisture free conditions. The solution was left overnight at room temperature. The separated solid was filtered, dried and crystallised from absolute ethanol to give 2 g yellowish needles (58% yield), m.p. 165-6°.

(ii) Using Thionyl Chloride—

To a well shaken suspension of 3.57 g (0.01 m) of oxime (II) in chloroform (35 ml), was added 1.7 ml thionyl chloride (0.0226 m) gradually at 30-35° and the reaction mixture was left at the same temperature for four hours. The sticky mass obtained on removal of the solvent solidified on trituration with methanol. The solid on crystallisation from absolute ethanol afforded 2.1 g yellow needles (62% yield), m.p. 165-6°.

(iii) Using Polyphosphoric acid—

3.57 g (0.01 m) of oxime (II) was heated with 8 ml of PPA (5 : 3 of P₂O₅ and orthophosphoric acid) for 8 hours on a water bath. On cooling to room-temperature the reaction mixture was poured in crushed ice with continuous stirring, when a solid was separated. The residue was chromatographed on silica gel. Elution of the column with Benzene-Methanol (5 : 1) gave the required pyrrolidone which was recrystallised from ethanol in pale yellow needles (2.37 g), m.p. 165-6°. ir (KBr) : ν_{\max} . 1735 (C=O of five membered ring) and 1685 (C=O of tert. amido gr.) cm⁻¹, nmr δ (CDCl₃) 1.2 (s, 1, CH), 2.25 (s, 3, ArCH₃), 2.55 (d, 2, COCH₂), 3.2 (d, 2, NCH₂), 3.8 (s, 6, OCH₃) and 7.0 (m, 7, ArH). Mass : M⁺ m/e 339. Adopting the identical conditions, other compounds of the type VI (Table 3) have been synthesised.

3-(2'-methoxy-5'-methylphenyl)-4-(4'-methoxybenzamido) butyric acid (VIIa) :

1.69 g (0.005 m) pyrrolidone (VIa) was refluxed with 1N ethanolic NaOH (30 ml) for 6 hours. The excess of ethanol was distilled off and residue dissolved in water and acidified with dil. HCl to give a solid which was crystallised from dil. ethanol, m.p. 162-3°, tlc 4 : 1 Benzene-Ethylacetate.

ir (KBr) : ν_{\max} . 2950-2700 (-OH of carboxylic group), 3350 (NH), 1700 (C=O of carboxylic group), 1680 1590 1260 (amide I, II and III resp.) cm⁻¹. nmr δ (CDCl₃) 1.2 (s, 1, CH), 2.25 (s, 3, ArCH₃), 2.85 (d, 2, NCH₂), 2.95 (d, 2, CH₂), 3.8 (s, 6, OCH₃), 7.0 (m, 7, ArH), 7.7 (s, 1, NH collapsed on D₂O exchange) and 11.0 (s, 1, COOH collapsed on D₂O exchange).

Mass : M⁺ m/e 357.

Other amido acids (VIIa-1) were obtained by following the similar procedure and are listed in Table 4.

3-(2'-methoxy-5'-methylphenyl)-4-aminobutyric acid (VIII)—

1.78 g (0.005 ml) amido acid (VIIa) was dissolved in 10N aq. NaOH (25 ml) and refluxed for 8 hrs. The content was cooled and acidified with dil. HCl and the solid thus obtained was passed through a column having silica gel as adsorbant, benzene-chloroform (1 : 1) as eluent and was recrystallised from dil. ethanol in pale yellow crystals, m.p. 154-5°.

Anal. Found : C, 63.11 ; H, 7.20 and N, 6.65%.

Calcd. for C₁₁H₁₅NO₃; C, 63.06 ; H, 7.17 and N, 6.69%.

ir (KBr) : showed that the amino acid exist in the form of Zwitter ion and the main absorptions are those arising from amine hydrochloride and carboxylate ion. ν 3010 2870 2600 2310 (prim. amine salt), 1610 (NH₃⁺ asym. bending), 1600 (COO⁻ asym. stretching), 1500 (NH₃⁺ sym. bending), 1410 (COO⁻

sym. stretching) and 1235 1125 (NH_3^+ rocking) cm^{-1} .
 nmr δ (CF_3COOH) 1.1 (s, 1, CH), 1.7 (s, 3, ArCH_3),
 two- CH_2 protons form a complex pattern with
 $-\text{NH}_3^+$ protons in the region 2.5-3.3 (s, 3, OCH_3)
 and 6.4 (m, 3, ArH).

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